

bidentate nature of the ligand. $\nu\text{N}-\text{O}$ appears at $\sim 920\text{ cm}^{-1}$ except in acetohydroxamic acid derivatives where it appears at 980 cm^{-1} . $\nu\text{Sn}-\text{C}$ bands can be observed at 510 and 610 cm^{-1} ¹⁰ in alkyltin (IV) compounds. Characteristic $\text{Ph}-\text{Sn}$ appears at $\sim 1070\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

In the products $\text{R}_2\text{Sn}_2\text{L}_2\text{O}_2$ (Table I, 1-4) the band present in the ligands at 440 cm^{-1} becomes intense suggesting the presence of $\text{Sn} \begin{array}{c} \diagup \text{O} \diagdown \\ \diagdown \text{O} \diagup \end{array} \text{Sn}$ ring¹⁰. Bidentate nature of ligand and presence of $\text{Sn} \begin{array}{c} \diagup \text{O} \diagdown \\ \diagdown \text{O} \diagup \end{array} \text{Sn}$ bridge

indicate that the compound involves two trigonal bipyramids joined through $\text{Sn}-\text{O}-\text{Sn}$ linkage.

The products $(\text{RSnL}_2)_2\text{O}$ (Table-I, 5-8) seem to involve two octahedrals with corner joined through $\text{Sn}-\text{O}-\text{Sn}$ linkage. Products RSnL_3 (Table-I, 9-10) and tris-(acetohydroxamato) phenyltin(IV) may be examples of seven co-ordinate mono-organotin(IV) derivatives. In the PMR spectra, apart from usual signals, only one methyl signal is observed at 7.5T for methyl of *p*-tolyl in *N-p*-tolyl benzhydroxamic acid derivative. It seems, that either ligand exchange is very fast or methyls of *p*-tolyl group are too far to be affected by the different ligand orientations in the molecule.

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References

1. P. G. HARRISON, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1973, 12, 1545.
2. P. G. HARRISON and T. J. KING, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton*, 1974, 2298.
3. P. G. HARRISON, T. J. KING and J. A. RICHARDS, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton*, 1975, 826.
4. P. G. HARRISON, T. J. KING and R. C. PHILLIPS, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton*, 1976, 2317.
5. B. PRADHAN and A. K. GOSH, *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1977, 131, 23.
6. A. H. BLATT, "Organic Syntheses", Vol. II, John Wiley, New York, 1950.
7. L. W. JONES and A. W. SCOTT, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 44, 407.
8. A. K. SAWYER, "Organotin Compounds, Vol. II, Marcel Dekker, Inc., New York, 1971.
9. C. K. NARULA and V. D. GUPTA, (Under communication).
10. T. TANAKA, *Organometal. Chem. Rev.*, 1970, 5, 1.

Synthesis of Ammonium, Sodium and Potassium Salts of Heteropoly Anion $[\text{SbV}_{12}\text{O}_{36}]^{7-}$

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THE existence of $[\text{V}_{12}\text{O}_{36}]^{12-}$ isopoly anion has been established by extensive studies on the formation and structure of phosphoro-12-vanadic heteropoly acids^{1,2}. They have established the existence of $[\text{PV}_{12}\text{O}_{36}]^{7-}$ heteropoly anion, in solution phase. The present communication deals with the synthesis of ammonium, sodium and potassium salts of a new heteropoly anion $[\text{SbV}_{12}\text{O}_{36}]^{7-}$.

The conditions of formation of these heteropoly salts have been established with the help of *pH* and thermometric titrations in the same manner as discussed in the previous communications³.

Ammoniumvanadoantimonate—35 ml of .2M NH_4VO_3 , 15 ml of glacial acetic acid and 50 ml of .013M potassiumpyroantimonate, $\text{K}[\text{Sb}(\text{OH})_6]$, were mixed together (*pH* 3.5) by continuous stirring for half an hour. The mixture was digested for 2 hours under controlled temperature of 80° in a thermostat. It was kept in a steam bath for three hours and then left for a few days. Intense deep brown compound separated after five days. For analysis of the compound vanadium was estimated volumetrically⁴ by potassium permanganate method and colorimetrically⁵ by hydrogen peroxide method. Antimony was estimated iodometrically⁵ and colorimetrically⁶ by rhodamine B method. Nitrogen and hydrogen were estimated by element estimation technique. From analysis: (Found: V, 31.450; Sb, 6.210; N, 5.012; H, 4.309 per cent. Calcd for $(\text{NH}_4)_7 [\text{SbV}_{12}\text{O}_{36}] 28\text{H}_2\text{O}$: V, 31.546; Sb, 6.289; N, 5.051; H, 4.324 per cent). The final representation of the formula was according to the views suggested by Spitsyn for complex heteropoly an ion $[\text{X}^n + \text{V}_{12}\text{O}_{36}]^{(12-n)-}$.

Sodiumvanadoantimonate—The reddish brown sodium salt of heteropoly anion $[\text{SbV}_{12}\text{O}_{36}]^{7-}$ was isolated by the same method as adopted for the synthesis of ammonium salt with slight variation in *pH*. Here 25 ml of .2M NaVO_3 solution, 25 ml of glacial acetic acid and 60 ml of .013 M $\text{K} [\text{Sb}(\text{OH})_6]$ solution were mixed together (*pH* 2.9) and a reddish brown powdery compound was separated after an interval of seven days by following the systematic treatments as discussed earlier. From analysis: (Found: V, 34.005; Sb, 6.691; Na, 8.901; H, 1.96 per cent. Calcd for $\text{Na}_7 [\text{SbV}_{12}\text{O}_{36}] 18\text{H}_2\text{O}$: V, 34.261; Sb, 6.796; Na, 8.969; H, 2.005 per cent). Sodium was estimated by flame photometric method.

Potassiumvanadoantimonate—Light brown amorphous type compound was separated from a solution

(pH 4.3) of 20 ml of .2M KVO_3 , 7 ml of glacial acetic acid and 40 ml of .013M $K[Sb(OH)_6]$ after an interval of twelve days, following the same treatment as has been described for the synthesis of the ammonium salt. From analysis : (Found V, 25.344; Sb, 5.051; K, 11.317; H, 3.798 per cent. Calcd for $K_7[SbV_{12}O_{36}] \cdot 46H_2O$: V, 25.383; Sb, 5.060; K, 11.323; H, 3.815 per cent. Potassium was estimated by flame photometric method.

Molecular Weight Determination—The molecular weights of all the salts of $[SbV_{12}O_{36}]^{7-}$ heteropoly anion, were successfully determined by the methods as has been done by Alexander⁷ and by Thilo and Krüger⁸ for the molecular weight determinations of certain inorganic polyacids and polyphosphates etc, in water and molten sodium sulphate decahydrate. This determination showed the molecular weights of the compounds $(NH_4)_7[SbV_{12}O_{36}] \cdot 28H_2O$, $Na_7[SbV_{12}O_{36}] \cdot 18H_2O$ and $K_7[SbV_{12}O_{36}] \cdot 46H_2O$ to be 1905, 1760 and 2375, as compared with the calculated values 1940, 1795 and 2411 respectively, which are in the range of fair agreement.

References

1. A. A. IVAKIN and L. D. KURBATOVA, *Koord. Khim.*, 1975, 1(11), 1481; 1976, 2(2), 217.
2. L. P. KAZANASKII, V. F. CHUVAEV and V. I. SPITSYN, *IVz. Akad. Nauk, U.S.S.R.*, 1976, 2, 256.
3. SALIL KUMAR ROY and G. C. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 1074; 1977, 54, 638.
4. W. W. SCOTT and N. H. FURMAN, "Standard Methods of Chemical Analysis", Technical Press Ltd., London, Vol. 1, p. 871.
5. A. I. VOGEL, "Text Book Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longman, Green and Co. Ltd., London, 1960, p. 576, 376.
6. F. D. SNELL and C. T. SNELL, "Colorimetric Analysis". D. Van Nostrand Company Inc., 1966, Vol. 2, p. 110.
7. G. B. ALEXANDER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 2094; 1953, 75, 2887.
8. E. THILO and G. KRÜGER, *Z. Electrochem.*, 1957, 61, 24.

Studies on 3-Bromo-2-Hydroxy-5-Methylacetophenone Oxime (BHMAO) as Metal Complexing Agent : Spectrophotometric Determination of Palladium (II), Copper (II), Nickel (II) and Cobalt (II)

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IN continuation of our studies on orthophenolic oximes^{1,2}, the present work reports the use of newly synthesized 3-bromo-2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone oxime (BHMAO) for the spectrophotometric determination of microgram quantities of Pd(II), Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II). The method can also be employed in the determination of Cu(II) and Ni(II) in a mixture directly.

Experimental

Apparatus and Reagents : A systronic spectrophotometer (type 103) was employed for recording spectra. The pH values of the solutions were measured with a systronic pH meter (type 322).

Standard stock solutions of palladium (II), copper (II), nickel (II) and cobalt (II) were prepared by dissolving appropriate amount of B.D.H. (AnalaR grade) $PdCl_2$, $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$, $NiCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ and $CoCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ in double distilled water containing dilute hydrochloric acid (0.5N) and standardized gravimetrically³. Ammonium hydroxide-ammonium chloride and acetic acid-sodium acetate were used to prepare buffers of different pH values.

The oxime of 3-bromo-2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone⁴ was prepared by refluxing its ethanolic solution with hydroxylamine hydrochloride and anhydrous sodium acetate for about two hours and purified by repeated crystallization from ethanol m.p. 198°.

Results and Discussion

It has been observed that the complexes can be extracted into nonaqueous solvents such as chloroform, carbontetrachloride, ethylacetate etc. The colours of the extracted complexes of Pd(II), Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) are yellow, buff, green and yellow respectively. Subsequent studies have been carried out in chloroform, because the extraction was better in chloroform than other nonaqueous solvents.

The method of Vosburg and Cooper⁵ was employed to determine the maximum absorption (λ_{max}) and number of the complexes. The absorption measurements show that only one complex is formed which has λ_{max} (nm) 400, 640, 600 and 400 for Pd(II), Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) complexes respectively.

Effect of pH :

A series of solutions (metal : ligand in 1:4) varying in pH was prepared and the absorbances were recorded after extraction of the complexes into chloroform at their λ_{max} . The range of pH value for no change in absorbance are reported in Table 1. The absorbance of the solutions decrease at higher or lower pH values.

Effect of reagent and ethanol concentration :

It was found that 6 fold excess of the reagent is necessary to attain the full colour development in all the cases under study. The reagent has negligible absorbance at the wave lengths selected for the measurements. The extracted complexes were found to be exhibit constant absorbance for atleast 48 hours.

It was also observed that the extraction of the complexes into chloroform depends upon the concentration of ethanol in aqueous medium. Above 30% (V/V) ethanol, the complex does not completely pass into chloroform layer in one extraction. In view of this 25% (V/V) concentration of ethanol was maintained throughout the work.